

Iatrogenic Lutembacher: *Percutaneous Mitral Balloon Valvuloplasty Sequel!*

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Description

The above 2-dimensional (2D), color flow Doppler and spectral Doppler transthoracic echocardiographic images (TTE) were obtained on a patient with dyspnea and history of rheumatic mitral valve stenosis, who underwent previous percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty (PMBV).

Figure A is a 2-D TTE apical 4-chamber view with superimposed color flow Doppler revealing residual left to right shunting across the fossa ovalis, along the superior inter-atrial septum (red arrow), the site of prior trans-septal puncture performed during the PMBV. Extensive calcifications of the posterior mitral valve annulus (yellow arrow) and dilatation of left atrium are also noted.

Figure B is a subcostal view, confirming the iatrogenic secundum atrial septal defect (ASD) with left to right shunting (red arrow), and the significantly dilated left atrium.

Figure C is a parasternal short axis 2-D TTE view across the mitral valve demonstrating tethering of the leaflets with restricted motion and extensive posterior annular calcification (yellow arrow). The mitral valve area measured by the planimetry method is approximately 1.2 cm², consistent with rheumatic severe mitral valve stenosis.

Figure D shows continuous wave spectral Doppler of the mitral valve inflow, with a measured pressure half-time of 150 milliseconds (ms), corresponding to a mitral valve area, by the pressure half-time method, of approximately 1.5 cm² (220/pressure half-time). This is likely an overestimation due to the faster equilibration of the mitral inflow in the setting of an ASD, resulting in a shorter pressure half time and a larger calculated mitral valve area.

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Discussion

Rheumatic heart disease is preventable, but remains highly endemic worldwide leading to increased morbidity and mortality [1]. Rheumatic mitral stenosis has shown some resurgence recently, necessitating innovative diagnostic and treatment options [2].

Percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty (PMBV) has emerged as a safe alternative to closed surgical mitral commissurotomy, with good prompt hemodynamic improvement [3]. Echocardiography, both transthoracic and transesophageal, is the primary modality employed in the diagnosis, assessment of PMBV eligibility and procedural guidance in rheumatic mitral stenosis [4].

The incidence of a residual ASD is high, nearly 67%, immediately post-PMBV, mostly commonly near the inferior vena cava side of the interatrial septum and in the fossa ovalis [5]. Most such ASD defects, however, close spontaneously and the incidence declines to nearly 9% by 6 months.

Restenosis of the mitral valve following PMBV is infrequent, but has been reported in 7% and up to 21% of symptomatic case [6]. Repeat PMBV has been shown to be feasible with good outcomes [7].

Lutembacher syndrome is defined as a concomitant ASD (congenital versus iatrogenic) and mitral stenosis (congenital versus acquired) and can be symptomatic [8]. Therefore, the coexistence of a residual ASD following PMBV and later mitral valve restenosis would satisfy the definition of iatrogenic Lutembacher syndrome [9].

PMBV has revolutionized the care of mitral stenosis worldwide for over 40 years as a safe and more readily available alternative to surgery [10]. Patient choice and technical feasibility, based on echocardiographic criteria, in addition to the availability of experienced operators, remain crucial in planning such procedure. Short and long term complications should be anticipated, especially, as in the case above, persistence of an iatrogenic ASD and restenosis of the mitral valve, creating the unfavorable hemodynamics of Lutembacher syndrome.

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